

Accsys Technologies

Ultra-durable modified wood

Accsys produces Accoya® wood: a sustainable, stable and durable modified wood to support the built environment and help tackle the embodied carbon challenge.

Highlights of innovative features:

- A proprietary acetylation process reduces the ability of the wood to absorb water, making it more dimensionally stable and no longer attractive to wood decaying fungi and insects.
- Accoya® provides a 25-year warranty in ground or freshwater and 50 year above ground.
- Accoya® wood is Cradle to Cradle Certified™ Gold and therefore suitable for Circular Economy business models.

As every piece of Accoya® wood has been modified through to its core, it provides the same performance no matter how the wood is cut, planed, drilled or shaped. Accoya® wood is durability class 1 and is ideal for many applications including window frames, doors, façades, cladding, decking, all without the use of preservatives.

Accoya® wood decking Venlo City Hall, the Netherlands

Company | Ownership of innovation

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